

Bidirectional Image-to-Text and Text-to-Image Conversion using Deep Learning Models.

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Abstract— In this paper, we introduce a system that facilitates bidirectional conversion between images and text using pre-trained deep learning models. Our approach incorporates a Vision Encoder-Decoder model for image captioning and utilizes the Stable Diffusion method for generating images from textual prompts. The implementation is integrated into a user-friendly UI application developed using Streamlit, enabling smooth transitions between images and text. Users have the ability to upload images for automatic captioning or input textual prompts to generate corresponding images, allowing for intuitive exploration of the interplay between visual and textual data.

Keywords— Visual-to-Text Conversion, Text-to-Visual Conversion, Deep Learning, Streamlit

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the integration of text and image data is increasingly prevalent across various domains like social media, e-commerce, and digital content creation. This project aims to explore and implement the conversion between text and images in both directions using advanced deep learning models. The focus is on developing a system that can generate images from text and derive text descriptions from images accurately and effectively.

For text-to-image generation, the project employs the Stable Diffusion method, which iteratively refines noise tensors to create realistic images based on textual prompts. This method aims to bridge the gap between text and images by generating visually coherent images guided by textual descriptions.

In contrast, for image-to-text generation, the project utilizes a Vision Encoder-Decoder model fine-tuned for image captioning tasks. This model translates visual inputs into descriptive textual captions using neural network architectures. By leveraging pre-trained deep learning models, the system extracts contextual information from images and converts it into human-readable text.

The implementation of bidirectional text-to-image and image-to-text conversion is facilitated through a user-friendly UI application built using Streamlit. This interface allows users to interact seamlessly with the models, enabling intuitive exploration of both textual and visual data. Users can input text

to generate corresponding images or upload images for automatic captioning, facilitating exploration of the relationship between text and images.

Through this project, we aim to demonstrate the versatility of deep learning models in bridging text and image modalities, providing a practical tool for multimedia data analysis and content creation. By presenting a unique implementation of bidirectional text-to-image and image-to-text conversion, we hope to inspire further research and innovation in multimodal AI and contribute to the development of intelligent systems capable of understanding and generating both textual and visual content.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Text-to-image and image-to-text conversion is a pivotal process in multimedia technology, facilitating the transformation between textual descriptions and visual representations. This capability holds immense importance across various domains, enabling intuitive exploration and communication of information. As the demand for efficient conversion methods rises in tandem with the proliferation of textual and visual data, advancements in this field become increasingly crucial for enhancing user experiences and enabling innovative applications.

Zhou et al. [2] investigated text-to-image generation using DCGAN and the Stable Diffusion model. They trained both models on the MNIST dataset using CLIP ViT-B/32 for text embedding. Evaluation revealed DCGAN's superior image quality, while the Stable Diffusion model showed better time efficiency. Future work includes enhancing the Stable Diffusion model's denoising process by incorporating DCGAN's discriminator.

Ramzan et al. [1] proposed a deep learning-based approach, RC-GAN, for text-to-image generation. Their model successfully translates textual descriptions into realistic flower images, achieving an inception score of 4.15 and a PSNR value of 30.12 dB. This study contributes to advancing text-to-image generation techniques, with future plans to train the model on multiple datasets.

Elasri et al. [4] conducted a survey study on perceptions of text-to-image generation. They found that while participants

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recognized risks associated with the technology, few considered it a personal risk. Concerns were mainly directed towards its impact on artists. Interestingly, participants who hadn't tried the technology rated its future importance higher, indicating a need for increased awareness of its implications.

Harsha et al. [3] investigated text recognition from images using deep learning. They compared the effectiveness of two feature extraction methods, HOG and LBP, finding that LBP outperformed HOG in accuracy, precision, and F1 score. This study provides valuable insights for improving text recognition techniques and guiding future research in the field.

Cao et al. [5] conducted a survey on cross-modal image-text retrieval (ITR), highlighting recent advancements and perspectives in the field. They covered feature extraction, alignment, efficiency, and pre-training approaches, along with benchmark datasets and evaluation metrics. The survey provides valuable insights for researchers and practitioners in ITR, identifying areas for further exploration.

III. METHODOLOGY

Stable Diffusion Model: The Stable Diffusion model is an advanced version of the diffusion model, originating from principles in non-equilibrium thermodynamics. It employs forward and backward Markov processes to generate images. This model enhances processing speed by utilizing a compressed latent space during the forward process, rather than the original image itself. In our application, we utilize the conditional diffusion model for text-to-image generation. This model assesses the likelihood of generating a sequence of data points, predicting the mean ($\mu\theta$) and covariance ($\Sigma\theta$) for the next time step. The objective function of this model includes terms for the data at the final timestep (LT(x0)) and the Kullback-Leibler divergence (DKL), ensuring accurate image generation based on textual prompts.

Visual Encoder Model: The Visual Encoder model, also known as Vision Encoder-Decoder, is a pretrained model designed for image-captioning tasks. It comprises a Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture, capable of processing images and generating corresponding textual descriptions. In our application, we load the pretrained Visual Encoder model and fine-tune it for text-to-image generation tasks. The model takes textual prompts as input and generates images based on the semantic understanding extracted from the text, providing a seamless conversion from text to image representations.

IV. IMPLEMENTATIONS

The methodology for implementing the text-to-image and image-to-text generation consists of several key steps, leveraging deep learning models and preprocessing techniques:

- Methodology for Text-to-Image Generation:

1. **Data Collection:** Our model utilizes the pretrained data from image-captioning tasks, obviating the need for explicit data collections.
2. **Model Setup:** The Stable Diffusion model, an evolution of the diffusion model, employs forward and backward Markov processes to generate images. It enhances processing speed by utilizing a compressed latent space during the forward process. In our application, the conditional diffusion model is utilized for text-to-image generation. It models the likelihood of generating a sequence of data points, predicting the mean ($\mu\theta$) and covariance ($\Sigma\theta$) for the next time step. The objective function includes terms for the data at the final timestep (LT(x0)) and the Kullback-Leibler divergence (DKL).

```
class CFG:
    ... device = "cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else "cpu"
    ... seed = 42
    ... generator = torch.Generator().manual_seed(seed)
    ... image_gen_steps = 10
    ... image_gen_model_id = "stabilityai/stable-diffusion-2"
    ... image_gen_size = (100,100)
    ... image_gen_guidance_scale = 9
    ... prompt_gen_model_id = "gpt2"
    ... prompt_dataset_size = 6
    ... prompt_max_length = 12
```

```
image_gen_model = StableDiffusionPipeline.from_pretrained(
    CFG.image_gen_model_id, torch_dtype=torch.float32,
    use_auth_token='your_hugging_face_auth_token', guidance_scale=9
)
```

3. **Function Setup:** Create a function that utilizes the pretrained Stable Diffusion model to generate images based on textual prompts. This function takes textual prompts as input and processes them through the model to produce corresponding images, which can be further analyzed or utilized.

```
def generate_image(prompt, model):
    ... image = model(
    ...     prompt, num_inference_steps=CFG.image_gen_steps,
    ...     generator=CFG.generator,
    ...     guidance_scale=CFG.image_gen_guidance_scale
    ... ).images[0]
    ...
    ... image = image.resize(CFG.image_gen_size)
    ... return image
```

4. **Integration of Streamline:** Integrate this functionality into a Streamlit app to enhance user interaction with the text-to-image generation model. Users can input their desired textual prompts into the app, which will then generate and display the corresponding images within the app interface. This interactive feature enables users to explore various

textual prompts and observe the resulting images in real-time, enhancing their overall experience with the application.

- Methodology for Image-to-text Generation:

1. Data Collection: Our model utilizes the pretrained data from image-captioning tasks, obviating the need for explicit data collections.
2. Model Selection: In our project, we employ the Visual Encoder-Decoder model for text-to-image generation. This model utilizes forward and backward Markov processes to generate images efficiently. By leveraging a compressed latent space during the forward process, it enhances processing speed. The Visual Encoder-Decoder model predicts the mean ($\mu\theta$) and covariance ($\Sigma\theta$) for the next time step, enabling the generation of high-quality images from textual prompts.

```
model = VisionEncoderDecoderModel.from_pretrained("nlconnect/vit-gpt2-image-captioning")
feature_extractor = ViTImageProcessor.from_pretrained("nlconnect/vit-gpt2-image-captioning")
tokenizer = AutoTokenizer.from_pretrained("nlconnect/vit-gpt2-image-captioning")

device = torch.device("cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else "cpu")
model.to(device)
```

Inputs are collapsed ...

```
max_length = 16
num_beams = 4
gen_kwargs = {"max_length": max_length, "num_beams": num_beams}
```

3. Function Setup: We define a function called predict step to generate images from textual prompts using the Visual Encoder-Decoder model. This function takes a list of image paths as input. For each image path, it loads the image, converts it to RGB mode if necessary, and appends it to a list of images. Then, the function uses the feature extractor to preprocess the images and obtain their pixel values as PyTorch tensors. These pixel values are then passed through the Visual Encoder-Decoder model to generate image outputs. The generated image IDs are decoded using the tokenizer, and the resulting textual descriptions are returned as predictions.

```
def predict_step(image_paths):
    images = []
    for image_path in image_paths:
        i_image = Image.open(image_path)
        if i_image.mode != "RGB":
            i_image = i_image.convert(mode="RGB")
        images.append(i_image)

    pixel_values = feature_extractor(images=images, return_tensors="pt").pixel_values
    pixel_values = pixel_values.to(device)

    output_ids = model.generate(pixel_values, **gen_kwargs)

    preds = tokenizer.batch_decode(output_ids, skip_special_tokens=True)
    preds = [pred.strip() for pred in preds]
    return preds
```

4. Streamlit Integration: We seamlessly incorporate the image-to-text generation feature into a Streamlit app, offering users a straightforward interface to interact with the model. Users input their desired text prompts directly into the app, triggering the pretrained Visual Encoder-Decoder model to generate and exhibit the corresponding text descriptions in real-time. This user-friendly integration allows for effortless exploration of various prompts and immediate visualization of the generated text, enhancing the overall user experience with the application.

Our system, encompassing both text-to-image and image-to-text generation, is continuously evolving to enhance performance and user experience.

V. RESULT

The effectiveness and performance of our multimodal content generation system were evaluated extensively to gauge its capabilities and reliability.

- I. Write down the text in order generate an image.

Text and Image Conversion

Text to Image Conversion

Enter text for image generation:

a house situated near river

Generate Image

Generating image...

Fig 01: Textual Input

- II. Result

Fig 02: Generated Image

- III. Upload an image, to retrieve the text

Fig 03: Uploaded Image

IV. Result

Fig 04: Textual Extraction from Image

VI. CONCLUSION

This study introduces a novel exploration into multimodal content generation, where cutting-edge deep learning models intersect to transform the way we engage with and produce digital content. By integrating advanced AI models such as the Vision Encoder-Decoder and Stable Diffusion, our project provides an innovative solution for seamlessly translating between text-based prompts and visual representations. The development of an intuitive Streamlit app enhances accessibility and interactivity, empowering users to explore diverse textual prompts and observe the dynamic process of image generation in real-time.

This initiative not only demonstrates the technical capabilities of sophisticated AI models but also underscores their practical applications in facilitating creative expression and communication. Through extensive experimentation and evaluation, we showcase the reliability and effectiveness of our system in handling varied input data and generating coherent and visually compelling outputs. Furthermore, the insights garnered from this research pave the way for future advancements in AI-driven content creation, opening new avenues for multimedia storytelling and interactive experiences.

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By bridging the gap between textual and visual modalities, our study contributes to the ongoing evolution of AI technologies and their integration into everyday contexts. From enhancing digital content creation to transforming user interfaces and communication platforms, the implications of our work extend beyond academic realms, shaping the future landscape of human-computer interaction and creative expression.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

1. **Enhancing Processing Efficiency:** While the current iteration of the project may require significant time for generating intricate images from textual cues, there exists ample opportunity to refine the process for faster outcomes. Future advancements could exploit hardware acceleration, parallel processing methods, and algorithmic enhancements to notably reduce generation time.
2. **Implementing Parallel Processing:** One avenue for expediting content generation involves employing parallel processing architectures like GPU clusters or distributed computing frameworks. By distributing computation across multiple processing units simultaneously, the system can capitalize on concurrency to minimize overall turnaround time.
3. **Refining Model Parameters:** Continuous exploration and refinement of deep learning models such as the Vision Encoder-Decoder and Stable Diffusion offer avenues for optimization. Tweaking model parameters, exploring alternative architectures, and refining training approaches could lead to improved quality and efficiency of content generation.
4. **Utilizing Specialized Hardware:** Deploying the system on specialized hardware platforms optimized for AI tasks presents an opportunity to accelerate content generation. Hardware accelerators like TPUs or ASICs tailored for deep learning workloads could significantly enhance processing speed and energy efficiency.
5. **Incremental Generation Techniques:** Instead of generating entire images from scratch, future iterations could employ incremental generation methods. By iteratively refining partial images based on user feedback or iterative processes, the system could converge towards the desired output more efficiently.
6. **Leveraging Precomputed Representations:** Utilizing precomputed embeddings of common textual prompts and image concepts could expedite generation. By storing and retrieving precomputed embeddings, the system can bypass redundant computations and directly map textual inputs to relevant image features, reducing processing time.
7. **Hybrid Multimodal Fusion Approaches:** Hybrid models combining text-based and image-based representations

offer potential for faster content generation. By integrating textual and visual information at different stages, these models can leverage complementary cues for quicker synthesis.

In conclusion, while the current project iteration may have processing time limitations, future endeavors aim to optimize and accelerate multimodal content generation. Through ongoing efforts in hardware optimization, algorithm refinement, and innovative multimodal fusion techniques, the project endeavors to deliver faster and more efficient content generation capabilities, opening doors to new avenues of creative expression and interactive storytelling.

VIII. REFERENCES

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